

Table 1. Donors of brown spot resistance in the Punjab, 1980 kharif.

IET No.	Designation	Source	Disease score ^a
7366	RNRO 1429	T. Hamsa/ Rasi	1
7367	RNR 27033	(T712/TNI)//HR 35	1
7343	KAU 23372	MN 54-42 mutant	3
7349	Co 32-20-66	-	3
7353	TNAU 13932/2	-	3
7364	RNRO 1446	T. Hamsa/ Rasi	3
7368	RNR 36718	(GEB 24/Sigadis)//(IR8/RNR 8102)	3
7417	R243-3041	IR7516(IR2071-625-1-252/205-3-521-3-3)	3
7497	CR294-28-1	(IR20/Zenith)// Malagkit Sungsong	3
7513	HPU5048-Pep 9-1B	JC 98/Kulu	3
7547	RP1442-2-2-3-5	Rasi/ K 46-15-B ₂	3
7145	CR263-889	T 141/Baok/T 141	3
6978	CR141-5036 CRRP5	(N22/TN1)//(T90/IR8)	3
7261	RP897-3790-30-1	Rasi/Mettasanna	3
6151	CR141-60-58-2-295	(N22/TNI)//(T90/IRS)	3
6686	IR42 (IR2071-586-5-6)	IR2042/CR 94-13	3
7291	PY 1	Ponni/IR8	3
-	Susceptible check7		

^a1976 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale of 1-9.

Table 2. Distribution of scores of resistance donors of brown spot of rice at PAU Rice Research Sub-Station, Gurdaspur, Punjab.

Score ^a	Leaf area infected	Resistance donors	
		Number	Percent
1	Less than 1%	2	0.35
3	1-5%	15	2.63
5	5-25%	467	81.93
7	25-50%	79	13.86
9	More than 50%	7	1.22

^a1976 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale.

entries were scored resistant; 15 were moderately resistant (Table 1). The distribution of scores is in Table 2. The resistant and moderately resistant donors are being used in Punjab breeding programs. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Gall midge infestation in a monthly-planted trial

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A 10-m² plot of BG34-8 rice variety was transplanted on the first of each calendar month beginning in March 1977 and ending in February 1979 at Batalagoda. Infestation of gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* was assessed by counting the infested hills in the total area planted at 3, 4, and 5 weeks after transplanting. After each count the galls were removed to avoid subsequent recounting.

The total number of hills sampled and the total infested hills at 3, 4, and 5 weeks after transplanting were used to calculate the percentage of gall midge infestation for 3 particular planting dates. Gall midge infestation was bimodal with a major peak in the December planting and a minor peak in the June planting. Furthermore, data on the mean rainfall for the 2 years show that the infestations peaked 2 months after the peak rainfall (see figure). These findings are being used to plan field screening tests such as the International Rice Gall Midge Nursery and the Gall Midge Biotype study. ■

Gall midge infestation and rainfall at Central Rice Breeding Station, Sri Lanka.

Chemical differences in rice varieties susceptible or resistant to gall midge and stem borer

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Gall midge *Orseolia (Pachydropis) oryzae* and yellow stem borer *Tryporyza incertulas* are two major internal feeder

pests of rice. Varietal differences in resistance to these pests have long been observed. To understand the mechanism of resistance, we undertook biochemical studies of selected resistant and susceptible varieties.

Because the gall midge attacks the vegetative shoot apex and the stem borer attacks the stem, 1-cm-long vegetative shoot apices and 2.54-cm-long

stems of the respective resistant and susceptible varieties were collected from 80-day-old healthy plants. Fresh plant samples were lyophilized for 6 hours, and 300 mg of lyophilized samples were extracted in 80% ethanol by grinding with mortar and pestle, and then filtered. Total free amino acids, phenol, and soluble sugars were chemically analyzed as per standard procedures using the ethanol extract of the material. The data for gall midge and stem borer resistance are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Results indicated that varieties PTB 18, PTB 21, and Leuang 152, which are highly resistant to gall midge, had relatively higher content of free amino acids and phenols and less sugars in their shoot apices than the susceptible varieties Jaya and IR8. In the case of the stem borer, on the other hand, the stems of both TKM6 (resistant) and Ratna (moderately resistant), a derivative of

Table 1. Biochemical constituents of vegetative shoot apices of selected rice varieties resistant and susceptible to gall midge. CRRI, Cuttack, India.

Variety	Reaction ^a to gall midge	Biochemical constituents (mg/g dry tissue)		
		Free amino acids	Phenols	Soluble sugars
PTB 18	R	24.8	5.5	12.0
PTB 21	R	32.5	7.8	10.8
Leuang 152	R	15.4	4.6	10.7
Jaya	S	9.3	4.4	19.0
IR8	S	9.7	3.8	19.7

^aR = resistant, S = susceptible.

Table 2. Biochemical constituents of stems of selected rice varieties resistant and susceptible to yellow stem borer. CRRI, Cuttack, India.

Variety	Reaction ^a to yellow stem borer	Biochemical constituents (mg/g dry tissue)		
		Free amino acids	Phenols	Soluble sugars
TKM6	R	2.0	2.5	21.2
Ratna	MR	3.9	1.8	30.5
IR8	S	13.7	4.4	50.3

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible.

the cross TKM6/IR8, have less amino acids, phenols, and sugars than the susceptible IR8. However, it was not determined whether the relative levels of

free amino acids, phenols, and soluble sugars were related to the resistance of these varieties to gall midge and stem borers. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Drought resistance

Rice varietal reactions to iron toxicity on acid sulfate soil

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In 3 seasons, 420 rices were screened for iron toxicity tolerance in an acid sulfate soil in a farmer's field in Albay Province, Philippines. The soil was a Sulfaquept (pH 3.5, organic carbon 1.2% active iron 2.5%, active manganese 0.001%, exchangeable sulfate 0.27%, and available phosphorus 7 mg/kg).

The field was puddled and harrowed after broadcasting 50 kg N/ha and 25 kg P/ha. Three-week-old seedlings, raised in a normal seedbed, were planted in three 3-m rows at a 20 × 20 cm spacing in randomized complete blocks replicated 3 times. A resistant check and a susceptible check were among the rices tested. The field was irrigated from a nearby stream. The plants were scored 4 weeks after transplanting for iron toxicity on foliar symptoms and general appearance,

using the scale 1 to 9 (1 = almost normal plant, and 9 = almost dead or dead plant). A score of 3 or lower indicated tolerance.

Table 1 summarizes the results. Forty-one rices showed tolerance for iron toxicity. Outstanding among them were IR36, IR3839-1, IR4442-165-1-3-2,

Table 1. Distribution of iron toxicity scores in field mass screening of rices during 3 seasons on an acid sulfate soil, Malinao, Albay, Philippines.

Varieties tested	Season	Rices (no.)	Score ^a distribution								
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
IRON 1978	1979 dry	262	0	0	36	166	57	2	1	0	0
1979 GEU Elite	1979 wet	85	0	0	0	5	15	33	23	9	0
1980 GEU Elite	1980 dry	73	0	0	5	39	26	3	0	0	0
Total		420	0	0	41	210	98	38	24	0	0

^aOn the scale 1 to 9 (1 = almost normal plant, 9 = almost dead or dead plant).

Table 2. Iron toxicity scores and grain yield of 7 selected rices in 3 seasons on an acid sulfate soil, Albay, Philippines.^a

Variety or line	1979 dry		1979 wet		1980 dry			
	Score	Yield (t/ha)	Score	Yield (t/ha)	Score	Yield (t/ha)		
IR26	4.8	1.7	f	7.2	^b	Not tested		
IR36	3.3	2.5	de	Not tested	^b	3.7	5.2	cde
IR42	Not tested			6.0		5.3	5.9	abc
IR44	Not tested			5.2	2.1	4.0	6.3	abc
IR46	4.0	3.2	bc	4.5	2.6	4.0	6.4	ab
IR4422-180-2	Not tested			5.0	2.7	4.7	4.6	def
IR4683-54-2	2.5	4.5	a	5.0	2.4	3.0	6.7	a

^aIn a column, values followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. The plants were scored 4 weeks after transplanting, on the 1-9 scale. ^bNot harvested.